

Sustainability analysis in agriculture using Linguistic Pythagorean Neutrosophic number through Einstein aggregation operators

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Abstract:

The Linguistic Pythagorean Neutrosophic (LPN) set is a powerful framework for handling uncertainty in assessments by integrating linguistic variables with Pythagorean Neutrosophic numbers (PNNs). In this study, we define new fundamental operations on Linguistic Pythagorean Neutrosophic Numbers (LPNNs) based on Einstein operations and examine their interrelationships. To address the challenges of LPNN fusion, we propose several LPN aggregation operators, namely the LPN Einstein Weighted Averaging (LPNEWA), and LPN Einstein Order Weighted Averaging (LPNEOWG) operators, and investigate their key characteristics. To demonstrate the proposed methodology's usefulness, we present an illustrative case study in sustainability agriculture. This case study highlights the practicality and effectiveness of the proposed decision-making model.

Keywords: Linguistic Pythagorean Neutrosophic set; LPN Einstein Weighted Average Operator, LPN Einstein Order Weighted Average Operator, Multi-Criteria Decision Making

i. Introduction

In 1998, Smarandache [1] introduced the concept of Neutrosophic sets (N_{set}), as an extension of intuitionistic fuzzy sets (IF_{set}), which provides a more comprehensive framework for handling uncertainty. Unlike IF_{sets} , those that are characterized by degrees of truth and falsity, N_{set} incorporates an additional dimension of uncertainty, enabling decision-makers to evaluate problems in terms of independent truth (T), indeterminacy (I), and falsity (F) values. This independence makes N_{set} a more powerful and generalized mathematical framework for representing and processing vague or imprecise information. Since its inception, researchers have extensively studied [2-5] both the theoretical foundations and applications of N_{sets} . Linguistic variables (LV_s) are used to express qualitative evaluations in complex decision-making. Zadeh [6] concept of LV_s for preference information in fuzzy reasoning gained broad research interest and led to further advancements in decision-making (DM) science. Fang and Ye [7] first introduced linguistic neutrosophic numbers (LNN_s), incorporating linguistic values for truth, indeterminacy, and falsity, and enabling the use of

all three kinds of linguistic information simultaneously. They further developed score and accuracy functions, along with aggregation operators, for effective decision-making. Recently, many researchers [8-12] have been exploring the applications, enhancements, and integration of LNN_s into various decision-making frameworks and fuzzy logic systems.

Zhao [13] introduced generalized aggregation operators based on IF_{sets} and showed that the arithmetic aggregation (AA) and geometry aggregation (GA) are special cases of these operators. These operators are derived using the algebraic sum and product of number sets, corresponding to the Archimedes t-conorm and t-norm for defining union and intersection operations. Wang and Liu [14] developed several *IFEA* operators and demonstrated that the Einstein aggregation operator offers better results compared to the AA operator. Zhao and Wei [15] introduced the *IFEHA* and *IFEHG* operators. Guo et al. [16] applied the Einstein operations to hesitant fuzzy sets. Later Li et al. [17] introduced the generalized Neutrosophic number for the Einstein aggregation operator. Recently, numerous researchers [18-20] have been exploring the Neutrosophic Einstein operator and its application in various decision-making processes. When combined with LNN_s , the Einstein operators enable effective aggregation of linguistic values involving truth, indeterminacy, and falsity probabilities. This integration enhances decision-making by managing uncertainty and offering smooth aggregation methods, such as weighted or geometric averages. Recently, many researchers [21-23] have focused on the use of the Einstein operator with LNN_s to manage uncertain or vague data in real-world decision-making settings.

1.2 Motivation

Aggregation operators are vital in decision support systems for consolidating information and ranking alternatives. While traditional algebraic T-norm and S-norm operators lack flexibility and robustness, Einstein T-norm and S-norm provide a superior alternative with smooth approximation properties. To enhance decision support systems, we develop Linguistic Pythagorean Neutrosophic Einstein Operators (LPNEO), enabling more effective aggregation of uncertain information. In sustainable agriculture, decision-making is often challenged by imprecise data, conflicting expert opinions, and dynamic environmental conditions. Tasks such as selecting appropriate crop varieties, optimizing resource allocation and infrastructure, or assessing the environmental impact of farming practices typically involve uncertain, incomplete, or ambiguous information. By integrating LPNEO, these challenges are effectively addressed, enabling more accurate handling of uncertainty and vagueness in agricultural decision processes.

1.3 Novelty

- This study extends the Einstein T-norm and T-conorm to LPNEO, improving their capability to manage uncertainty and imprecision more effectively.
- Establish a Multi-Attribute Group Decision-Making (MAGDM) framework based on the newly introduced Einstein operators, providing a more efficient and accurate approach for decision-making in uncertain environments.

1.4 Objective

The key research objectives and contributions of this study are:

- Extending the Einstein T-norm and T-conorm to LPNEO to enhance flexibility and robustness.
- Introducing various LPNEOs, including LPN Einstein averaging operators, LPN Einstein geometric operators, and LPN Einstein hybrid operators, while exploring their fundamental properties.
- Developing a novel decision-making (DM) method based on the proposed operators to effectively address MAGDM problems in real-world scenarios.

2 Preliminaries

In this section, some fundamental concepts related to LPNS have been presented.

Definition: 1 Neutrosophic set (N_{set}): [1] Let Θ be a universe set. A N_{set} , \tilde{A} on Θ is defined as $\tilde{A} = \{(x, T_{\tilde{A}}(x), I_{\tilde{A}}(x), F_{\tilde{A}}(x)): x \in \Theta\}$, where $T_{\tilde{A}}(x): \Theta \rightarrow]0,1[+$ is said to be the TMF, which represents the degree of confidence, $I_{\tilde{A}}(x): \Theta \rightarrow]0,1[+$ is said to be the IMF, which represents the degree of uncertainty, and $F_{\tilde{A}}(x): \Theta \rightarrow]0,1[+$ is said to be the FMF, which represents the degree of skepticism, respectively of the element $x \in \Theta$ in \tilde{A}_N , such that $0 \leq T_{\tilde{A}}(x) + I_{\tilde{A}}(x) + F_{\tilde{A}}(x) \leq 3$.

Definition: 2 Pythagorean Neutrosophic sets (PN_{set}): [2] Let Θ be a universe set. A PN_{set} \tilde{A} on Θ is defined as $\tilde{A} = \{(x, T_{\tilde{A}}(x), I_{\tilde{A}}(x), F_{\tilde{A}}(x)): x \in \Theta\}$, such that $(T_{\tilde{A}}(x))^2 + (I_{\tilde{A}}(x))^2 + (F_{\tilde{A}}(x))^2 \leq 2$, where $T_{\tilde{A}}(x): \Theta \rightarrow]0,1[+$ is the TMF, $I_{\tilde{A}}(x): \Theta \rightarrow]0,1[+$ is the IMF, and $F_{\tilde{A}}(x): \Theta \rightarrow]0,1[+$ is the FMF.

Definition: 3 Linguistic Neutrosophic Set (LN_{set}): [3] Let Θ be a universe set. A LN_{set} in Θ is defined as $\tilde{A} = \{(x, T_{\tilde{A}}(x), I_{\tilde{A}}(x), F_{\tilde{A}}(x)): x \in \Theta\}$, where $T_{\tilde{A}}(x): \Theta \rightarrow]0,1[+$ is the LTMF, $I_{\tilde{A}}(x): \Theta \rightarrow]0,1[+$ is the LIMF, and $F_{\tilde{A}}(x): \Theta \rightarrow]0,1[+$ is the LFMF. Each membership functions $T_{\tilde{A}}(x)$, $I_{\tilde{A}}(x)$, and $F_{\tilde{A}}(x)$ takes linguistic values from a predefined linguistic term set \tilde{S} .

Definition: 4 Linguistic Pythagorean Neutrosophic Set (LPN_{set}): [24] Let Θ be a universe set. A LPN_{set} in Θ is defined as $\tilde{A} = \{(x, T_{\tilde{A}}(x), I_{\tilde{A}}(x), F_{\tilde{A}}(x)): x \in \Theta\}$, such that $(T_{\tilde{A}}(x))^2 + (I_{\tilde{A}}(x))^2 + (F_{\tilde{A}}(x))^2 \leq 2$, where $T_{\tilde{A}}(x)$, $I_{\tilde{A}}(x)$, and $F_{\tilde{A}}(x)$ are represented using linguistic terms.

Definition: 5 Einstein T-Norm and S-Norm [5]: For arbitrary two real numbers $(\tilde{a}, \tilde{b}) \in [0, 1]$, the Einstein sums and product are defined as follows:

$$\tilde{S}_E(\tilde{a}, \tilde{b}) = \tilde{a} \oplus_{\epsilon} \tilde{b} = \frac{\tilde{a} + \tilde{b}}{1 + \tilde{a} \cdot \tilde{b}}, \quad \tilde{T}_E(\tilde{a}, \tilde{b}) = \tilde{a} \otimes_{\epsilon} \tilde{b} = \frac{\tilde{a} \cdot \tilde{b}}{1 + (1 - \tilde{a}) \cdot (1 - \tilde{b})}, \quad \forall (\tilde{a}, \tilde{b}) \in [0, 1]^2.$$

Garg [24] introduced new different functions for ordering the alternatives using the score function with an accuracy function to build the comparison approach of LPNNS.

Definition: 6 Let $v = (\zeta_{\alpha_1}, \zeta_{\beta_1}, \zeta_{\gamma_1})$ be a LPNNS. Then the score function \mathcal{T} and accuracy function \mathcal{H} of \mathcal{A} are defined as:

$$\mathfrak{I}(\mathcal{A}) = \zeta \sqrt{\frac{k^2 + \alpha_1^2 - \beta_1^2 - \gamma_1^2}{3}}$$

$$\mathfrak{H}(\mathcal{A}) = \zeta \sqrt{\alpha_1^2 + \beta_1^2 - \gamma_1^2}$$

For comparing two LPNNs \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{B} , the comparison method is given as:

- i. if $\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{A}) > \mathcal{T}(\mathcal{B})$, then $\mathcal{A} > \mathcal{B}$;
- ii. if $\mathcal{T}(\mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{T}(\mathcal{B})$, then
 - if $\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{A}) < \mathcal{H}(\mathcal{B})$, then $\mathcal{A} < \mathcal{B}$;
 - if $\mathcal{H}(\mathcal{A}) = \mathcal{H}(\mathcal{B})$, then $\mathcal{A} \sim \mathcal{B}$.

3 Einstein Operation of Linguistic Pythagorean Neutrosophic Numbers (LPNNs)

Linguistic Pythagorean Neutrosophic Numbers (LPNNs) offer a novel and powerful framework for handling uncertainty, overcoming the limitations of traditional linear approaches. Unlike previous works that focus on fuzzy or standard neutrosophic numbers, LPNNs combine the enhanced flexibility of Pythagorean logic with the interpretability of linguistic terms. The application of Einstein operations, known for their nonlinear, bounded, and smooth aggregation behavior, further strengthens the robustness of this approach in complex decision-making scenarios. In this section, we introduce the Einstein sum (\oplus_ϵ) and Einstein product (\otimes_ϵ) operations within the LPNN framework, along with two aggregation operators such as LPN Einstein Weighted Average (LPNEWA) operator, and LPN Einstein Ordered Weighted Average (LPNEOWA) operator.

Definition: 7 Let $\mathcal{P} = (\zeta_{\alpha_1}, \zeta_{\beta_1}, \zeta_{\gamma_1})$ and $\mathcal{Q} = (\zeta_{\alpha_2}, \zeta_{\beta_2}, \zeta_{\gamma_2})$ be two LPNNs and $\lambda \geq 0$, then the Einstein operation of \oplus_ϵ and \otimes_ϵ under the LPNN are defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 i. \quad \mathcal{P} \oplus_\epsilon \mathcal{Q} &= \left(\zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{t^2(\alpha_1^2 + \alpha_2^2)}{t^4 + \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2}}, \zeta_t \frac{\beta_1 \beta_2}{\sqrt{t^4 + (t^2 - \beta_1^2)(t^2 - \beta_2^2)}}, \zeta_t \frac{\gamma_1 \gamma_2}{\sqrt{t^4 + (t^2 - \gamma_1^2)(t^2 - \gamma_2^2)}} \right); \\
 ii. \quad \mathcal{P} \otimes_\epsilon \mathcal{Q} &= \left(\zeta_t \frac{\alpha_1 \alpha_2}{\sqrt{t^4 + (t^2 - \alpha_1^2)(t^2 - \alpha_2^2)}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{t^2(\beta_1^2 + \beta_2^2)}{t^4 + \beta_1^2 \beta_2^2}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{t^2(\gamma_1^2 + \gamma_2^2)}{t^4 + \gamma_1^2 \gamma_2^2}} \right); \\
 iii. \quad \lambda \mathcal{P} &= \left(\zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{(t^2 + \alpha_1^2)^\lambda - (t^2 - \alpha_1^2)^\lambda}{(t^2 + \alpha_1^2)^\lambda + (t^2 - \alpha_1^2)^\lambda}}, \zeta_t \frac{\sqrt{2} \beta_1^\lambda}{\sqrt{(2t^2 - \beta_1^2)^\lambda + (\beta_1^2)^\lambda}}, \zeta_t \frac{\sqrt{2} \gamma_1^\lambda}{\sqrt{(2t^2 - \gamma_1^2)^\lambda + (\gamma_1^2)^\lambda}} \right); \\
 iv. \quad \mathcal{P}^\lambda &= \left(\zeta_t \frac{\sqrt{2} \alpha_1^\lambda}{\sqrt{(2t^2 - \alpha_1^2)^\lambda + (\alpha_1^2)^\lambda}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{(t^2 + \beta_1^2)^\lambda - (t^2 - \beta_1^2)^\lambda}{(t^2 + \beta_1^2)^\lambda + (t^2 - \beta_1^2)^\lambda}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{(t^2 + \gamma_1^2)^\lambda - (t^2 - \gamma_1^2)^\lambda}{(t^2 + \gamma_1^2)^\lambda + (t^2 - \gamma_1^2)^\lambda}} \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem: 1 Let $\mathcal{P} = (\zeta_{\alpha_1}, \zeta_{\beta_1}, \zeta_{\gamma_1})$ and $\mathcal{Q} = (\zeta_{\alpha_2}, \zeta_{\beta_2}, \zeta_{\gamma_2})$ be two LPNNs and $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \lambda_3 \geq 0$, then the Einstein operation of \oplus_ϵ and \otimes_ϵ have the following performance:

- i. $\mathcal{P} \oplus_\epsilon \mathcal{Q} = \mathcal{Q} \oplus_\epsilon \mathcal{P}$;
- ii. $\mathcal{P} \otimes_\epsilon \mathcal{Q} = \mathcal{Q} \otimes_\epsilon \mathcal{P}$;
- iii. $\lambda(\mathcal{P} \oplus_\epsilon \mathcal{Q}) = \lambda \mathcal{P} \oplus_\epsilon \lambda \mathcal{Q}$;
- iv. $(\mathcal{P} \otimes_\epsilon \mathcal{Q})^\lambda = \mathcal{P}^\lambda \otimes_\epsilon \mathcal{Q}^\lambda$;

- v. $(\lambda_1 \oplus_{\epsilon} \lambda_2)\mathcal{P} = \lambda_1\mathcal{P} \oplus_{\epsilon} \lambda_2\mathcal{P};$
- vi. $\mathcal{P}^{\lambda_1} \otimes_{\epsilon} \mathcal{P}^{\lambda_2} = \mathcal{P}^{\lambda_1+\lambda_2}.$

Proof: Performance (i) and (ii) are easy. So, we proves (iii), and (v).

According to Definition 5, we can get

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P} \oplus_{\epsilon} \mathcal{Q} &= \left(\zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{t^2(\alpha_1^2+\alpha_2^2)}{t^4+\alpha_1^2\alpha_2^2}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{\beta_1\beta_2}{t^4+(t^2-\beta_1^2)(t^2-\beta_2^2)}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{\gamma_1\gamma_2}{t^4+(t^2-\gamma_1^2)(t^2-\gamma_2^2)}} \right); \\ &= \left(\zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{(t^2+\alpha_1^2)(t^2+\alpha_2^2)-(t^2-\alpha_1^2)(t^2-\alpha_2^2)}{(t^2+\alpha_1^2)(t^2+\alpha_2^2)+(t^2-\alpha_1^2)(t^2-\alpha_2^2)}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2\beta_1^2\beta_2^2}{\beta_1^2\beta_2^2+(2t^2-\beta_1^2)(2t^2-\beta_2^2)}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2\gamma_1^2\gamma_2^2}{\gamma_1^2\gamma_2^2+(2t^2-\gamma_1^2)(2t^2-\gamma_2^2)}} \right); \\ &= \left(\zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{\tilde{a}-\tilde{b}}{\tilde{a}+\tilde{b}}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2\tilde{c}}{\tilde{c}+\tilde{d}}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2\tilde{e}}{\tilde{e}+\tilde{f}}} \right) \end{aligned}$$

where $\tilde{a} = (t^2 + \alpha_1^2)(t^2 + \alpha_2^2), \tilde{b} = (t^2 - \alpha_1^2)(t^2 - \alpha_2^2), \tilde{c} = \beta_1^2\beta_2^2, \tilde{d} = (2t^2 - \beta_1^2)(2t^2 - \beta_2^2), \tilde{e} = \gamma_1^2\gamma_2^2, \tilde{f} = (2t^2 - \gamma_1^2)(2t^2 - \gamma_2^2).$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{P} \oplus_{\epsilon} \mathcal{Q} &= \lambda \left(\zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{\tilde{a}-\tilde{b}}{\tilde{a}+\tilde{b}}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2\tilde{c}}{\tilde{c}+\tilde{d}}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2\tilde{e}}{\tilde{e}+\tilde{f}}} \right) \\ &= \left(\zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{(t^2+\alpha_1^2)^\lambda(t^2+\alpha_2^2)^\lambda-(t^2-\alpha_1^2)^\lambda(t^2-\alpha_2^2)^\lambda}{(t^2+\alpha_1^2)^\lambda(t^2+\alpha_2^2)^\lambda+(t^2-\alpha_1^2)^\lambda(t^2-\alpha_2^2)^\lambda}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2(\beta_1^2)^\lambda(\beta_2^2)^\lambda}{(\beta_1^2)^\lambda(\beta_2^2)^\lambda+(2t^2-\beta_1^2)^\lambda(2t^2-\beta_2^2)^\lambda}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2(\gamma_1^2)^\lambda(\gamma_2^2)^\lambda}{(\gamma_1^2)^\lambda(\gamma_2^2)^\lambda+(2t^2-\gamma_1^2)^\lambda(2t^2-\gamma_2^2)^\lambda}} \right) \\ &= \left(\zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{\tilde{a}^\lambda-\tilde{b}^\lambda}{\tilde{a}^\lambda+\tilde{b}^\lambda}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2\tilde{c}^\lambda}{\tilde{c}^\lambda+\tilde{d}^\lambda}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2\tilde{e}^\lambda}{\tilde{e}^\lambda+\tilde{f}^\lambda}} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Now,

$$\lambda\mathcal{P} = \left(\zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{(t^2+\alpha_1^2)^\lambda-(t^2-\alpha_1^2)^\lambda}{(t^2+\alpha_1^2)^\lambda+(t^2-\alpha_1^2)^\lambda}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2(\beta_1^2)^\lambda}{(\beta_1^2)^\lambda+(2t^2-\beta_1^2)^\lambda}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2(\gamma_1^2)^\lambda}{(\gamma_1^2)^\lambda+(2t^2-\gamma_1^2)^\lambda}} \right) = \left(\zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{\tilde{a}_1-\tilde{b}_1}{\tilde{a}_1+\tilde{b}_1}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2\tilde{c}_1}{\tilde{c}_1+\tilde{d}_1}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2\tilde{e}_1}{\tilde{e}_1+\tilde{f}_1}} \right)$$

$$\text{and } \lambda\mathcal{Q} = \left(\zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{(t^2+\alpha_2^2)^\lambda-(t^2-\alpha_2^2)^\lambda}{(t^2+\alpha_2^2)^\lambda+(t^2-\alpha_2^2)^\lambda}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2(\beta_2^2)^\lambda}{(\beta_2^2)^\lambda+(2t^2-\beta_2^2)^\lambda}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2(\gamma_2^2)^\lambda}{(\gamma_2^2)^\lambda+(2t^2-\gamma_2^2)^\lambda}} \right) = \left(\zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{\tilde{a}_2-\tilde{b}_2}{\tilde{a}_2+\tilde{b}_2}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2\tilde{c}_2}{\tilde{c}_2+\tilde{d}_2}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2\tilde{e}_2}{\tilde{e}_2+\tilde{f}_2}} \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{then } \lambda\mathcal{P} \oplus_{\epsilon} \lambda\mathcal{Q} &= \left(\zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{\tilde{a}_1-\tilde{b}_1}{\tilde{a}_1+\tilde{b}_1}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2\tilde{c}_1}{\tilde{c}_1+\tilde{d}_1}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2\tilde{e}_1}{\tilde{e}_1+\tilde{f}_1}} \right) \oplus_{\epsilon} \left(\zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{\tilde{a}_2-\tilde{b}_2}{\tilde{a}_2+\tilde{b}_2}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2\tilde{c}_2}{\tilde{c}_2+\tilde{d}_2}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2\tilde{e}_2}{\tilde{e}_2+\tilde{f}_2}} \right) \\ &= \left(\zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{\tilde{a}_1\tilde{a}_2-\tilde{b}_1\tilde{b}_2}{\tilde{a}_1\tilde{a}_2+\tilde{b}_1\tilde{b}_2}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2\tilde{c}_1\tilde{c}_2}{\tilde{c}_1\tilde{c}_2+\tilde{d}_1\tilde{d}_2}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2\tilde{e}_1\tilde{e}_2}{\tilde{e}_1\tilde{e}_2+\tilde{f}_1\tilde{f}_2}} \right) \\ &= \left(\zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{(t^2+\alpha_1^2)^\lambda(t^2+\alpha_2^2)^\lambda-(t^2-\alpha_1^2)^\lambda(t^2-\alpha_2^2)^\lambda}{(t^2+\alpha_1^2)^\lambda(t^2+\alpha_2^2)^\lambda+(t^2-\alpha_1^2)^\lambda(t^2-\alpha_2^2)^\lambda}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2(\beta_1^2)^\lambda(\beta_2^2)^\lambda}{(\beta_1^2)^\lambda(\beta_2^2)^\lambda+(2t^2-\beta_1^2)^\lambda(2t^2-\beta_2^2)^\lambda}}, \zeta_t \sqrt{\frac{2(\gamma_1^2)^\lambda(\gamma_2^2)^\lambda}{(\gamma_1^2)^\lambda(\gamma_2^2)^\lambda+(2t^2-\gamma_1^2)^\lambda(2t^2-\gamma_2^2)^\lambda}} \right) \end{aligned}$$

where $\tilde{a}_1 = (t^2 + \alpha_1^2)^\lambda, \tilde{a}_2 = (t^2 + \alpha_2^2)^\lambda, \tilde{b}_1 = (t^2 - \alpha_1^2)^\lambda, \tilde{b}_2 = (t^2 - \alpha_2^2)^\lambda, \tilde{c}_1 = (\beta_1^2)^\lambda, \tilde{c}_2 = (\beta_2^2)^\lambda, \tilde{d}_1 = (2t^2 - \beta_1^2)^\lambda, \tilde{d}_2 = (2t^2 - \beta_2^2)^\lambda, \tilde{e}_1 = (\gamma_1^2)^\lambda, \tilde{e}_2 = (\gamma_2^2)^\lambda, \tilde{f}_1 = (2t^2 - \gamma_1^2)^\lambda, \tilde{f}_2 = (2t^2 - \gamma_2^2)^\lambda.$

Hence, we can obtain $\lambda(\mathcal{P} \oplus_\epsilon \mathcal{Q}) = \lambda\mathcal{P} \oplus_\epsilon \lambda\mathcal{Q}.$

Now, we prove the performance of (v):

$$\lambda_1\mathcal{P} = \left(\zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{(t^2+\alpha_1^2)^{\lambda_1} - (t^2-\alpha_1^2)^{\lambda_1}}{(t^2+\alpha_1^2)^{\lambda_1} + (t^2-\alpha_1^2)^{\lambda_1}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2(\beta_1^2)^{\lambda_1}}{(\beta_1^2)^{\lambda_1} + (2t^2-\beta_1^2)^{\lambda_1}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2(\gamma_1^2)^{\lambda_1}}{(\gamma_1^2)^{\lambda_1} + (2t^2-\gamma_1^2)^{\lambda_1}}} \right) = \left(\zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{\tilde{a}_1 - \tilde{b}_1}{\tilde{a}_1 + \tilde{b}_1}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2\tilde{c}_1}{\tilde{c}_1 + \tilde{d}_1}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2\tilde{e}_1}{\tilde{e}_1 + \tilde{f}_1}} \right),$$

$$\lambda_2\mathcal{P} = \left(\zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{(t^2+\alpha_2^2)^{\lambda_2} - (t^2-\alpha_2^2)^{\lambda_2}}{(t^2+\alpha_2^2)^{\lambda_2} + (t^2-\alpha_2^2)^{\lambda_2}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2(\beta_2^2)^{\lambda_2}}{(\beta_2^2)^{\lambda_2} + (2t^2-\beta_2^2)^{\lambda_2}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2(\gamma_2^2)^{\lambda_2}}{(\gamma_2^2)^{\lambda_2} + (2t^2-\gamma_2^2)^{\lambda_2}}} \right) = \left(\zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{\tilde{a}_2 - \tilde{b}_2}{\tilde{a}_2 + \tilde{b}_2}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2\tilde{c}_2}{\tilde{c}_2 + \tilde{d}_2}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2\tilde{e}_2}{\tilde{e}_2 + \tilde{f}_2}} \right),$$

where $\bar{a}_1 = (t^2 + \alpha_1^2)^{\lambda_1}, \bar{a}_2 = (t^2 + \alpha_2^2)^{\lambda_2}, \bar{b}_1 = (t^2 - \alpha_1^2)^{\lambda_1}, \bar{b}_2 = (t^2 - \alpha_2^2)^{\lambda_2}, \bar{c}_1 = (\beta_1^2)^{\lambda_1}, \bar{c}_2 = (\beta_2^2)^{\lambda_2}, \bar{d}_1 = (2t^2 - \beta_1^2)^{\lambda_1}, \bar{d}_2 = (2t^2 - \beta_2^2)^{\lambda_2}, \bar{e}_1 = (\gamma_1^2)^{\lambda_1}, \bar{e}_2 = (\gamma_2^2)^{\lambda_2}, \bar{f}_1 = (2t^2 - \gamma_1^2)^{\lambda_1}, \bar{f}_2 = (2t^2 - \gamma_2^2)^{\lambda_2}.$

$$\lambda_1\mathcal{P} \oplus_\epsilon \lambda_2\mathcal{P} = \left(\zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{\tilde{a}_1 - \tilde{b}_1}{\tilde{a}_1 + \tilde{b}_1}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2\tilde{c}_1}{\tilde{c}_1 + \tilde{d}_1}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2\tilde{e}_1}{\tilde{e}_1 + \tilde{f}_1}} \right) \oplus_\epsilon \left(\zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{\tilde{a}_2 - \tilde{b}_2}{\tilde{a}_2 + \tilde{b}_2}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2\tilde{c}_2}{\tilde{c}_2 + \tilde{d}_2}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2\tilde{e}_2}{\tilde{e}_2 + \tilde{f}_2}} \right)$$

$$= \left(\zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{\tilde{a}_1\tilde{a}_2 - \tilde{b}_1\tilde{b}_2}{\tilde{a}_1\tilde{a}_2 + \tilde{b}_1\tilde{b}_2}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2\tilde{c}_1\tilde{c}_2}{\tilde{c}_1\tilde{c}_2 + \tilde{d}_1\tilde{d}_2}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2\tilde{e}_1\tilde{e}_2}{\tilde{e}_1\tilde{e}_2 + \tilde{f}_1\tilde{f}_2}} \right)$$

$$= \left(\zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{(t^2+\alpha_1^2)^{\lambda_1+\lambda_2} - (t^2-\alpha_1^2)^{\lambda_1+\lambda_2}}{(t^2+\alpha_1^2)^{\lambda_1+\lambda_2} + (t^2-\alpha_1^2)^{\lambda_1+\lambda_2}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2(\beta_1^2)^{\lambda_1+\lambda_2}}{(\beta_1^2)^{\lambda_1+\lambda_2} + (2t^2-\beta_1^2)^{\lambda_1+\lambda_2}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2(\gamma_1^2)^{\lambda_1+\lambda_2}}{(\gamma_1^2)^{\lambda_1+\lambda_2} + (2t^2-\gamma_1^2)^{\lambda_1+\lambda_2}}} \right) = (\lambda_1 \oplus_\epsilon \lambda_2)\mathcal{P}.$$

Hence, $\lambda_1\mathcal{P} \oplus_\epsilon \lambda_2\mathcal{P} = (\lambda_1 \oplus_\epsilon \lambda_2)\mathcal{P}.$

4. LPN Einstein Aggregation Operators

4.1 LPN Einstein weighted average (LPNEWA) operator

Definition: 8 Let LPNN $\mathcal{P}_i = (\zeta_{\alpha_i}, \zeta_{\beta_i}, \zeta_{\gamma_i})$ in ζ , for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$. Then the LPNEWA operator is defined as: $LPNEWA(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n) = \omega_1\mathcal{P}_1 \oplus_\epsilon \omega_2\mathcal{P}_2 \oplus_\epsilon \omega_3\mathcal{P}_3 \oplus_\epsilon \dots \oplus_\epsilon \omega_n\mathcal{P}_n$, with the weight vector $\omega = (\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3, \dots, \omega_n)^T, \sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i = 1$ and $\omega_i \in [0,1]$.

Theorem: 2 Set a collection $\mathcal{P}_i = (\zeta_{\alpha_i}, \zeta_{\beta_i}, \zeta_{\gamma_i})$ in ζ , for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$, then the fusion value generated by LPNEWA operator is also a LPNN and

$$LPNEWA(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n) = \left(\zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{\prod_{i=1}^n (t^2+\alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i} - \prod_{i=1}^n (t^2-\alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i}}{\prod_{i=1}^n (t^2+\alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^n (t^2-\alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2 \prod_{i=1}^n (\beta_i^2)^{\omega_i}}{\prod_{i=1}^n (\beta_i^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^n (2t^2-\beta_i^2)^{\omega_i}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2 \prod_{i=1}^n (\gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i}}{\prod_{i=1}^n (\gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^n (2t^2-\gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i}}} \right) \text{ with}$$

the weight vector $\omega = (\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3, \dots, \omega_n)^T, \sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i = 1$ and $\omega_i \in [0,1]$.

Proof: When $n = 2$, $LPNEWA(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2) = \omega_1\mathcal{P}_1 \oplus_\epsilon \omega_2\mathcal{P}_2.$

By definition 5 , we get

$$\omega_1 \mathcal{P}_1 = \left(\zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{(t^2 + \alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1} - (t^2 - \alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1}}{(t^2 + \alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1} + (t^2 - \alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2(\beta_1^2)^{\omega_1}}{(\beta_1^2)^{\omega_1} + (2t^2 - \beta_1^2)^{\omega_1}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2(\gamma_1^2)^{\omega_1}}{(\gamma_1^2)^{\omega_1} + (2t^2 - \gamma_1^2)^{\omega_1}}} \right),$$

$$\omega_2 \mathcal{P}_2 = \left(\zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{(t^2 + \alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2} - (t^2 - \alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2}}{(t^2 + \alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2} + (t^2 - \alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2(\beta_2^2)^{\omega_2}}{(\beta_2^2)^{\omega_2} + (2t^2 - \beta_2^2)^{\omega_2}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2(\gamma_2^2)^{\omega_2}}{(\gamma_2^2)^{\omega_2} + (2t^2 - \gamma_2^2)^{\omega_2}}} \right).$$

$$\omega_1 \mathcal{P}_1 \oplus_\epsilon \omega_2 \mathcal{P}_2 = \left(\zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{\frac{(t^2 + \alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1} - (t^2 - \alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1}}{(t^2 + \alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1} + (t^2 - \alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1}} + \frac{(t^2 + \alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2} - (t^2 - \alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2}}{(t^2 + \alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2} + (t^2 - \alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2}}}{1 + \frac{(t^2 + \alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1} - (t^2 - \alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1}}{(t^2 + \alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1} + (t^2 - \alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1}} + \frac{(t^2 + \alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2} - (t^2 - \alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2}}{(t^2 + \alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2} + (t^2 - \alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2}}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{\frac{2(\beta_1^2)^{\omega_1}}{(\beta_1^2)^{\omega_1} + (2t^2 - \beta_1^2)^{\omega_1}} + \frac{2(\beta_2^2)^{\omega_2}}{(\beta_2^2)^{\omega_2} + (2t^2 - \beta_2^2)^{\omega_2}}}{1 + \frac{2(\beta_1^2)^{\omega_1}}{(\beta_1^2)^{\omega_1} + (2t^2 - \beta_1^2)^{\omega_1}} + \frac{2(\beta_2^2)^{\omega_2}}{(\beta_2^2)^{\omega_2} + (2t^2 - \beta_2^2)^{\omega_2}}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{\frac{2(\gamma_1^2)^{\omega_1}}{(\gamma_1^2)^{\omega_1} + (2t^2 - \gamma_1^2)^{\omega_1}} + \frac{2(\gamma_2^2)^{\omega_2}}{(\gamma_2^2)^{\omega_2} + (2t^2 - \gamma_2^2)^{\omega_2}}}{1 + \frac{2(\gamma_1^2)^{\omega_1}}{(\gamma_1^2)^{\omega_1} + (2t^2 - \gamma_1^2)^{\omega_1}} + \frac{2(\gamma_2^2)^{\omega_2}}{(\gamma_2^2)^{\omega_2} + (2t^2 - \gamma_2^2)^{\omega_2}}}} \right)$$

$$= \left(\zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{((t^2 + \alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1} - (t^2 - \alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1}) \cdot ((t^2 + \alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2} - (t^2 - \alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2})}{((t^2 + \alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1} + (t^2 - \alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1}) \cdot ((t^2 + \alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2} + (t^2 - \alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2})}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2(\beta_1^2)^{\omega_1} \cdot (\beta_2^2)^{\omega_2}}{(\beta_1^2)^{\omega_1} (\beta_2^2)^{\omega_2} + (2t^2 - \beta_1^2)^{\omega_1} \cdot (2t^2 - \beta_2^2)^{\omega_2}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2(\gamma_1^2)^{\omega_1} \cdot (\gamma_2^2)^{\omega_2}}{(\gamma_1^2)^{\omega_1} (\beta_2^2)^{\omega_2} + (2t^2 - \gamma_1^2)^{\omega_1} \cdot (2t^2 - \gamma_2^2)^{\omega_2}}} \right)$$

Hence, $LPNEWA(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2) = \omega_1 \mathcal{P}_1 \oplus_\epsilon \omega_2 \mathcal{P}_2$, valid for $n = 2$.

When the consequence is valid for $n = k$, we have

$$LPNEWA(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_k) = \left(\zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{\prod_{i=1}^k (t^2 + \alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i} - \prod_{i=1}^k (t^2 - \alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i}}{\prod_{i=1}^k (t^2 + \alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^k (t^2 - \alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2 \prod_{i=1}^k (\beta_i^2)^{\omega_i}}{\prod_{i=1}^k (\beta_i^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^k (2t^2 - \beta_i^2)^{\omega_i}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2 \prod_{i=1}^k (\gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i}}{\prod_{i=1}^k (\gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^k (2t^2 - \gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i}}} \right).$$

When $n = k + 1$, we have

$$LPNEWA(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_{k+1}) = LPNEWA(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_k \oplus_\epsilon \omega_{k+1} \mathcal{P}_{k+1})$$

$$= \left(\zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{\prod_{i=1}^k (t^2 + \alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i} - \prod_{i=1}^k (t^2 - \alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i}}{\prod_{i=1}^k (t^2 + \alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^k (t^2 - \alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2 \prod_{i=1}^k (\beta_i^2)^{\omega_i}}{\prod_{i=1}^k (\beta_i^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^k (2t^2 - \beta_i^2)^{\omega_i}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2 \prod_{i=1}^k (\gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i}}{\prod_{i=1}^k (\gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^k (2t^2 - \gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i}}} \right)$$

$$\oplus_\epsilon \left(\zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{(t^2 + \alpha_{k+1}^2)^{\omega_{k+1}} - (t^2 - \alpha_{k+1}^2)^{\omega_{k+1}}}{(t^2 + \alpha_{k+1}^2)^{\omega_{k+1}} + (t^2 - \alpha_{k+1}^2)^{\omega_{k+1}}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2(\beta_{k+1}^2)^{\omega_{k+1}}}{(\beta_{k+1}^2)^{\omega_{k+1}} + (2t^2 - \beta_{k+1}^2)^{\omega_{k+1}}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2(\gamma_{k+1}^2)^{\omega_{k+1}}}{(\gamma_{k+1}^2)^{\omega_{k+1}} + (2t^2 - \gamma_{k+1}^2)^{\omega_{k+1}}}}} \right)$$

$$= \left(\zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{\prod_{i=1}^{k+1} (t^2 + \alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i} - \prod_{i=1}^{k+1} (t^2 - \alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i}}{\prod_{i=1}^{k+1} (t^2 + \alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^{k+1} (t^2 - \alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2 \prod_{i=1}^{k+1} (\beta_i^2)^{\omega_i}}{\prod_{i=1}^{k+1} (\beta_i^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^{k+1} (2t^2 - \beta_i^2)^{\omega_i}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2 \prod_{i=1}^{k+1} (\gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i}}{\prod_{i=1}^{k+1} (\gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^{k+1} (2t^2 - \gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i}}} \right).$$

Therefore, $LPNEWA(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n)$ holds for any n .

Hence, Theorem 2 is proved.

Theorem: 3 Set a collection $\mathcal{P}_i = (\zeta_{\alpha_i}, \zeta_{\beta_i}, \zeta_{\gamma_i})$, $\mathcal{Q}_i = (\zeta_{\tilde{\alpha}_i}, \zeta_{\tilde{\beta}_i}, \zeta_{\tilde{\gamma}_i})$ in ζ , for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$, be two LPNNs with the weight vector $\omega = (\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3, \dots, \omega_n)^T$, $\sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i = 1$ and $\omega_i \in [0, 1]$. We can deduce the following properties:

- i. *Idempotency: If $\mathcal{P}_i = (\zeta_{\alpha_i}, \zeta_{\beta_i}, \zeta_{\gamma_i}) = (\zeta_{\alpha}, \zeta_{\beta}, \zeta_{\gamma})$ for all i , then*

$$\text{LPNEWA}(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n) = (\zeta_\alpha, \zeta_\beta, \zeta_\gamma).$$

ii. *Monotonicity:* If $\mathcal{P}_i \leq \mathcal{Q}_i$, that is, $\zeta_{\alpha_i} \leq \zeta_{\tilde{\alpha}_i}$, $\zeta_{\beta_i} \geq \zeta_{\tilde{\beta}_i}$, and $\zeta_{\gamma_i} \geq \zeta_{\tilde{\gamma}_i}$, then we have

$$\text{LPNEWA}(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n) \leq \text{LPNEWA}(\mathcal{Q}_1, \mathcal{Q}_2, \mathcal{Q}_3, \dots, \mathcal{Q}_n).$$

iii. *Boundedness:* Suppose $\mathcal{P}^- = \min(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n)$, $\mathcal{P}^+ = \max(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n)$, then

$$\mathcal{P}^- \leq \text{LPNEWA}(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n) \leq \mathcal{P}^+.$$

Proof: Let $\mathcal{P}_i = (\zeta_{\alpha_i}, \zeta_{\beta_i}, \zeta_{\gamma_i})$, $\mathcal{Q}_i = (\zeta_{\tilde{\alpha}_i}, \zeta_{\tilde{\beta}_i}, \zeta_{\tilde{\gamma}_i})$ in ζ , for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$, be two collections of LPNNs.

Then

i. when $\mathcal{P}_i = (\zeta_{\alpha_i}, \zeta_{\beta_i}, \zeta_{\gamma_i}) = (\zeta_\alpha, \zeta_\beta, \zeta_\gamma)$ for all i , one has

$$\text{LPNEWA}(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n)$$

$$= \left(\zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{\prod_{i=1}^n (t^2 + \alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i} - \prod_{i=1}^n (t^2 - \alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i}}{\prod_{i=1}^n (t^2 + \alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^n (t^2 - \alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2 \prod_{i=1}^n (\beta_i^2)^{\omega_i}}{\prod_{i=1}^n (\beta_i^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^n (2t^2 - \beta_i^2)^{\omega_i}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2 \prod_{i=1}^n (\gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i}}{\prod_{i=1}^n (\gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^n (2t^2 - \gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i}}} \right),$$

$$= \left(\zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{(t^2 + \alpha_i^2)^{\prod_{i=1}^n \omega_i} - (t^2 - \alpha_i^2)^{\prod_{i=1}^n \omega_i}}{(t^2 + \alpha_i^2)^{\prod_{i=1}^n \omega_i} + (t^2 - \alpha_i^2)^{\prod_{i=1}^n \omega_i}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2(\beta_i^2)^{\prod_{i=1}^n \omega_i}}{(\beta_i^2)^{\prod_{i=1}^n \omega_i} + (2t^2 - \beta_i^2)^{\prod_{i=1}^n \omega_i}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2(\gamma_i^2)^{\prod_{i=1}^n \omega_i}}{(\gamma_i^2)^{\prod_{i=1}^n \omega_i} + (2t^2 - \gamma_i^2)^{\prod_{i=1}^n \omega_i}}} \right),$$

$$= \left(\zeta_{t(\frac{\alpha_i}{t})}, \zeta_{t(\frac{\beta_i}{t})}, \zeta_{t(\frac{\gamma_i}{t})} \right) = \mathcal{P}_i.$$

ii. For $\mathcal{P}_i \leq \mathcal{Q}_i$, then $\omega_i \mathcal{P}_i \leq \omega_i \mathcal{Q}_i$.

So, we can obtain $\bigoplus_{\epsilon=1}^n \omega_i \mathcal{P}_i \leq \bigoplus_{\epsilon=1}^n \omega_i \mathcal{Q}_i$. For $\text{LPNEWA}(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n) = \bigoplus_{\epsilon=1}^n \omega_i \mathcal{P}_i$,

and $\text{LPNEWA}(\mathcal{Q}_1, \mathcal{Q}_2, \mathcal{Q}_3, \dots, \mathcal{Q}_n) = \bigoplus_{\epsilon=1}^n \omega_i \mathcal{Q}_i$, then we can get $\text{LPNEWA}(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n) \leq \text{LPNEWA}(\mathcal{Q}_1, \mathcal{Q}_2, \mathcal{Q}_3, \dots, \mathcal{Q}_n)$.

iii. Since $\mathcal{P}^- = \min(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n)$, $\mathcal{P}^+ = \max(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n)$. By the previous proof (ii), we have

$$\text{LPNEWA}(\mathcal{P}^-, \mathcal{P}^-, \mathcal{P}^-, \dots, \mathcal{P}^-) \leq \text{LPNEWA}(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n) \leq \text{LPNEWA}(\mathcal{P}^+, \mathcal{P}^+, \mathcal{P}^+, \dots, \mathcal{P}^+).$$

In addition, by the previous proof (i), we have

$$\text{LPNEWA}(\mathcal{P}^+, \mathcal{P}^+, \mathcal{P}^+, \dots, \mathcal{P}^+) = \mathcal{P}^+, \text{ and } \text{LPNEWA}(\mathcal{P}^-, \mathcal{P}^-, \mathcal{P}^-, \dots, \mathcal{P}^-) = \mathcal{P}^-.$$

From all the above, we can get $\mathcal{P}^- \leq \text{LPNEWA}(\mathcal{P}^+, \mathcal{P}^+, \mathcal{P}^+, \dots, \mathcal{P}^+) = \mathcal{P}^+$.

4.2 LPN Einstein order weighted average (LPNEOWA) operator

Definition: 9 Set a LPNNs $\mathcal{P}_i = (\zeta_{\alpha_i}, \zeta_{\beta_i}, \zeta_{\gamma_i})$ in ζ , for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$, then the LPNEOWA operator is

defined as: $\text{LPNEOWA}(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n) = \omega_1 \mathcal{P}_{\rho(1)} \oplus_{\epsilon} \omega_2 \mathcal{P}_{\rho(2)} \oplus_{\epsilon} \omega_3 \mathcal{P}_{\rho(3)} \oplus_{\epsilon} \dots \oplus_{\epsilon} \omega_n \mathcal{P}_{\rho(n)}$,

where $(\rho(1), \rho(2), \rho(3), \dots, \rho(n))$ is a permutation of $(i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n)$, such that $\mathcal{P}_{\rho(i-1)} \geq \mathcal{P}_{\rho(i)}$ for each i , with the weight vector $\omega = (\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3, \dots, \omega_n)^T$, $\sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i = 1$ and $\omega_i \in [0, 1]$.

Theorem: 4 Set a collection $\mathcal{P}_i = (\zeta_{\alpha_i}, \zeta_{\beta_i}, \zeta_{\gamma_i})$ in ζ , for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$, then the fusion result by LPNEOWA operator is obtained as:

$$LPNEOWA(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n) = \left(\zeta \frac{\prod_{i=1}^n (t^2 + \alpha_{\rho(i)}^2)^{\omega_i} - \prod_{i=1}^n (t^2 - \alpha_{\rho(i)}^2)^{\omega_i}}{t \sqrt{\prod_{i=1}^n (t^2 + \alpha_{\rho(i)}^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^n (t^2 - \alpha_{\rho(i)}^2)^{\omega_i}}}, \zeta \frac{2 \prod_{i=1}^n (\beta_{\rho(i)}^2)^{\omega_i}}{\prod_{i=1}^n (\beta_{\rho(i)}^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^n (2t^2 - \beta_{\rho(i)}^2)^{\omega_i}}, \zeta \frac{2 \prod_{i=1}^n (\gamma_{\rho(i)}^2)^{\omega_i}}{\prod_{i=1}^n (\gamma_{\rho(i)}^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^n (2t^2 - \gamma_{\rho(i)}^2)^{\omega_i}} \right),$$

where $(\rho(1), \rho(2), \rho(3), \dots, \rho(n))$ is a permutation of $(i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n)$, such that $\mathcal{P}_{\rho(i-1)} \geq \mathcal{P}_{\rho(i)}$ for each i , with the weight vector $\omega = (\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3, \dots, \omega_n)^T$, $\sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i = 1$ and $\omega_i \in [0, 1]$. Evidently, if $\omega = (\frac{1}{n}, \frac{1}{n}, \frac{1}{n}, \dots, \frac{1}{n})$, the LPNEOWA operator will reduce to LPNWA operator.

Theorem: 5 Set a collection $\mathcal{P}_i = (\zeta_{\alpha_i}, \zeta_{\beta_i}, \zeta_{\gamma_i})$, $\mathcal{Q}_i = (\zeta_{\tilde{\alpha}_i}, \zeta_{\tilde{\beta}_i}, \zeta_{\tilde{\gamma}_i})$ in ζ , for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$, be two LPNNs with the weight vector $\omega = (\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3, \dots, \omega_n)^T$, $\sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i = 1$ and $\omega_i \in [0, 1]$. We can deduce the following properties:

i. *Idempotency: If $\mathcal{P}_i = (\zeta_{\alpha_i}, \zeta_{\beta_i}, \zeta_{\gamma_i}) = (\zeta_{\alpha}, \zeta_{\beta}, \zeta_{\gamma})$ for all i , then*

$$LPNEOWA(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n) = (\zeta_{\alpha}, \zeta_{\beta}, \zeta_{\gamma}).$$

ii. *Monotonicity: If $\mathcal{P}_i \leq \mathcal{Q}_i$, that is, $\zeta_{\alpha_i} \leq \zeta_{\tilde{\alpha}_i}$, $\zeta_{\beta_i} \geq \zeta_{\tilde{\beta}_i}$, and $\zeta_{\gamma_i} \geq \zeta_{\tilde{\gamma}_i}$, then*

$$LPNEOWA(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n) \leq LPNEOWA(\mathcal{Q}_1, \mathcal{Q}_2, \mathcal{Q}_3, \dots, \mathcal{Q}_n).$$

iii. *Boundedness: Suppose $\mathcal{P}^- = \min(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n)$, $\mathcal{P}^+ = \max(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n)$, then*

$$\mathcal{P}^- \leq LPNEOWA(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n) \leq \mathcal{P}^+.$$

iv. *Commutativity: $\mathcal{Q}_i = (\zeta_{\tilde{\alpha}_i}, \zeta_{\tilde{\beta}_i}, \zeta_{\tilde{\gamma}_i})$ ($i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$) is any permutation of $\mathcal{P}_i = (\zeta_{\alpha_i}, \zeta_{\beta_i}, \zeta_{\gamma_i})$, then $LPNEOWA(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n) = LPNEOWA(\mathcal{Q}_1, \mathcal{Q}_2, \mathcal{Q}_3, \dots, \mathcal{Q}_n)$. The proof is similar to that of Theorem 3; therefore, we omit it here.*

4.3 LPN Einstein weighted geometry (LPNEWG) operator

Definition: 10 Let LPNNs $\mathcal{P}_i = (\zeta_{\alpha_i}, \zeta_{\beta_i}, \zeta_{\gamma_i})$ in ζ , for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$. Then the LPNEWG operator is defined as: $LPNEWG(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n) = \mathcal{P}_1^{\omega_1} \otimes_{\epsilon} \mathcal{P}_2^{\omega_2} \otimes_{\epsilon} \dots \mathcal{P}_n^{\omega_n}$, with the weight vector $\omega = (\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3, \dots, \omega_n)^T$, $\sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i = 1$ and $\omega_i \in [0, 1]$.

Theorem: 6 Set a collection $\mathcal{P}_i = (\zeta_{\alpha_i}, \zeta_{\beta_i}, \zeta_{\gamma_i})$ in ζ , for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$, then the fusion value generated by LPNEWG operator is also a LPNN and

$$LPNEWG(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n) = \left(\zeta \frac{2 \prod_{i=1}^n (\alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i}}{t \sqrt{\prod_{i=1}^n (\alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^n (2t^2 - \alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i}}}, \zeta \frac{\prod_{i=1}^n (t^2 + \beta_i^2)^{\omega_i} - \prod_{i=1}^n (t^2 - \beta_i^2)^{\omega_i}}{t \sqrt{\prod_{i=1}^n (t^2 + \beta_i^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^n (t^2 - \beta_i^2)^{\omega_i}}}, \zeta \frac{\prod_{i=1}^n (t^2 + \gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i} - \prod_{i=1}^n (t^2 - \gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i}}{t \sqrt{\prod_{i=1}^n (t^2 + \gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^n (t^2 - \gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i}}} \right) \text{ with}$$

the weight vector $\omega = (\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3, \dots, \omega_n)^T$, $\sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i = 1$ and $\omega_i \in [0, 1]$.

Proof: When $n = 2$, $LPNEWA(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2) = \mathcal{P}_1^{\omega_1} \otimes_{\epsilon} \mathcal{P}_2^{\omega_2}$.

By definition 5, we get

$$\mathcal{P}_1^{\omega_1} = \left(\zeta \frac{2(\alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1}}{t \sqrt{(\alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1} + (2t^2 - \alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1}}}, \zeta \frac{(t^2 + \beta_1^2)^{\omega_1} - (t^2 - \beta_1^2)^{\omega_1}}{t \sqrt{(t^2 + \beta_1^2)^{\omega_1} + (t^2 - \beta_1^2)^{\omega_1}}}, \zeta \frac{(t^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{\omega_1} - (t^2 - \gamma_1^2)^{\omega_1}}{t \sqrt{(t^2 + \gamma_1^2)^{\omega_1} + (t^2 - \gamma_1^2)^{\omega_1}}} \right),$$

$$\mathcal{P}_2^{\omega_2} = \left(\zeta \frac{2(\alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2}}{t \sqrt{(\alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2} + (2t^2 - \alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2}}}, \zeta \frac{(t^2 + \beta_2^2)^{\omega_2} - (t^2 - \beta_2^2)^{\omega_2}}{t \sqrt{(t^2 + \beta_2^2)^{\omega_2} + (t^2 - \beta_2^2)^{\omega_2}}}, \zeta \frac{(t^2 + \gamma_2^2)^{\omega_2} - (t^2 - \gamma_2^2)^{\omega_2}}{t \sqrt{(t^2 + \gamma_2^2)^{\omega_2} + (t^2 - \gamma_2^2)^{\omega_2}}} \right)$$

$$\mathcal{P}_1^{\omega_1} \otimes_{\epsilon} \mathcal{P}_2^{\omega_2} = \left(\zeta \sqrt{\frac{2(\alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1}}{(\alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1}(2t^2-\alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1}} \frac{2(\alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2}}{(\alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2}(2t^2-\alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2}}}, \zeta \sqrt{\frac{2(\alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1}}{(\alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1}(2t^2-\alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1}} \frac{2(\alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2}}{(\alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2}(2t^2-\alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2}}}, \zeta \sqrt{\frac{2(\alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1}}{(\alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1}(2t^2-\alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1}} \frac{2(\alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2}}{(\alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2}(2t^2-\alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2}}} \right)$$

$$= \left(\zeta \sqrt{\frac{2(\alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1} \cdot (\alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2}}{(\alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1}(\alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2} + (2t^2-\alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1}(2t^2-\alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2}}}, \zeta \sqrt{\frac{((t^2+\beta_1^2)^{\omega_1} - (t^2-\beta_1^2)^{\omega_1}) + ((t^2+\beta_2^2)^{\omega_2} - (t^2-\beta_2^2)^{\omega_2})}{((t^2+\beta_1^2)^{\omega_1} + (t^2-\beta_1^2)^{\omega_1}) + ((t^2+\beta_2^2)^{\omega_2} + (t^2-\beta_2^2)^{\omega_2})}}, \zeta \sqrt{\frac{((t^2+\gamma_1^2)^{\omega_1} - (t^2-\gamma_1^2)^{\omega_1}) + ((t^2+\gamma_2^2)^{\omega_2} - (t^2-\gamma_2^2)^{\omega_2})}{((t^2+\gamma_1^2)^{\omega_1} + (t^2-\gamma_1^2)^{\omega_1}) + ((t^2+\gamma_2^2)^{\omega_2} + (t^2-\gamma_2^2)^{\omega_2})}} \right)$$

$$= \left(\zeta \sqrt{\frac{2(\alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1} \cdot (\alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2}}{(\alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1}(\alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2} + (2t^2-\alpha_1^2)^{\omega_1}(2t^2-\alpha_2^2)^{\omega_2}}}, \zeta \sqrt{\frac{((t^2+\beta_1^2)^{\omega_1}) \cdot ((t^2+\beta_2^2)^{\omega_2}) - ((t^2-\beta_1^2)^{\omega_1}) \cdot ((t^2-\beta_2^2)^{\omega_2})}{((t^2+\beta_1^2)^{\omega_1}) \cdot ((t^2+\beta_2^2)^{\omega_2}) + ((t^2-\beta_1^2)^{\omega_1}) \cdot ((t^2-\beta_2^2)^{\omega_2})}}, \zeta \sqrt{\frac{((t^2+\gamma_1^2)^{\omega_1}) \cdot ((t^2+\gamma_2^2)^{\omega_2}) - ((t^2-\gamma_1^2)^{\omega_1}) \cdot ((t^2-\gamma_2^2)^{\omega_2})}{((t^2+\gamma_1^2)^{\omega_1}) \cdot ((t^2+\gamma_2^2)^{\omega_2}) + ((t^2-\gamma_1^2)^{\omega_1}) \cdot ((t^2-\gamma_2^2)^{\omega_2})}} \right)$$

Hence, $LPNEWG(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2) = \mathcal{P}_1^{\omega_1} \otimes_{\epsilon} \mathcal{P}_2^{\omega_2}$, valid for $n = 2$.

When the consequence is valid for $n = k$, we have

$$LPNEWG(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_k) = \left(\zeta \sqrt{\frac{2 \prod_{i=1}^k (\alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i}}{\prod_{i=1}^k (\alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^k (2t^2 - \alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i}}}, \zeta \sqrt{\frac{\prod_{i=1}^k ((t^2 + \beta_i^2)^{\omega_i}) - \prod_{i=1}^k ((t^2 - \beta_i^2)^{\omega_i})}{\prod_{i=1}^k ((t^2 + \beta_i^2)^{\omega_i}) + \prod_{i=1}^k ((t^2 - \beta_i^2)^{\omega_i})}}, \zeta \sqrt{\frac{\prod_{i=1}^k ((t^2 + \gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i}) - \prod_{i=1}^k ((t^2 - \gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i})}{\prod_{i=1}^k ((t^2 + \gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i}) + \prod_{i=1}^k ((t^2 - \gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i})}} \right)$$

When $n = k + 1$, we have

$$LPNEWG(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_{k+1}) = LPNEWG(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_k) \otimes_{\epsilon} \mathcal{P}_{k+1}^{\omega_{k+1}}$$

$$= \left(\zeta \sqrt{\frac{2 \prod_{i=1}^k (\alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i}}{\prod_{i=1}^k (\alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^k (2t^2 - \alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i}}}, \zeta \sqrt{\frac{\prod_{i=1}^k ((t^2 + \beta_i^2)^{\omega_i}) - \prod_{i=1}^k ((t^2 - \beta_i^2)^{\omega_i})}{\prod_{i=1}^k ((t^2 + \beta_i^2)^{\omega_i}) + \prod_{i=1}^k ((t^2 - \beta_i^2)^{\omega_i})}}, \zeta \sqrt{\frac{\prod_{i=1}^k ((t^2 + \gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i}) - \prod_{i=1}^k ((t^2 - \gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i})}{\prod_{i=1}^k ((t^2 + \gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i}) + \prod_{i=1}^k ((t^2 - \gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i})}} \right)$$

$$\otimes_{\epsilon} \left(\zeta \sqrt{\frac{2(\alpha_{k+1}^2)^{\omega_{k+1}}}{(\alpha_{k+1}^2)^{\omega_{k+1}}(2t^2-\alpha_{k+1}^2)^{\omega_{k+1}}}}, \zeta \sqrt{\frac{((t^2+\beta_{k+1}^2)^{\omega_{k+1}} - (t^2-\beta_{k+1}^2)^{\omega_{k+1}})}{((t^2+\beta_{k+1}^2)^{\omega_{k+1}} + (t^2-\beta_{k+1}^2)^{\omega_{k+1}})}}, \zeta \sqrt{\frac{((t^2+\gamma_{k+1}^2)^{\omega_{k+1}} - (t^2-\gamma_{k+1}^2)^{\omega_{k+1}})}{((t^2+\gamma_{k+1}^2)^{\omega_{k+1}} + (t^2-\gamma_{k+1}^2)^{\omega_{k+1}})}} \right)$$

$$= \left(\zeta \sqrt{\frac{2 \prod_{i=1}^{k+1} (\alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i}}{\prod_{i=1}^{k+1} (\alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^{k+1} (2t^2 - \alpha_i^2)^{\omega_i}}}, \zeta \sqrt{\frac{\prod_{i=1}^{k+1} ((t^2 + \beta_i^2)^{\omega_i}) - \prod_{i=1}^{k+1} ((t^2 - \beta_i^2)^{\omega_i})}{\prod_{i=1}^{k+1} ((t^2 + \beta_i^2)^{\omega_i}) + \prod_{i=1}^{k+1} ((t^2 - \beta_i^2)^{\omega_i})}}, \zeta \sqrt{\frac{\prod_{i=1}^{k+1} ((t^2 + \gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i}) - \prod_{i=1}^{k+1} ((t^2 - \gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i})}{\prod_{i=1}^{k+1} ((t^2 + \gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i}) + \prod_{i=1}^{k+1} ((t^2 - \gamma_i^2)^{\omega_i})}} \right)$$

Therefore, $LPNEWG(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n)$ holds for any n .

Hence, Theorem 6 is proved.

Theorem: 7 Set a collection $\mathcal{P}_i = (\zeta_{\alpha_i}, \zeta_{\beta_i}, \zeta_{\gamma_i})$, $\mathcal{Q}_i = (\zeta_{\tilde{\alpha}_i}, \zeta_{\tilde{\beta}_i}, \zeta_{\tilde{\gamma}_i})$ in ζ , for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$, be two LPNNs with the weight vector $\omega = (\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3, \dots, \omega_n)^T$, $\sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i = 1$ and $\omega_i \in [0,1]$. We can deduce the following properties:

i. *Idempotency: If $\mathcal{P}_i = (\zeta_{\alpha_i}, \zeta_{\beta_i}, \zeta_{\gamma_i}) = (\zeta_{\alpha}, \zeta_{\beta}, \zeta_{\gamma})$ for all i , then*

$$LPNEWG(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n) = (\zeta_{\alpha}, \zeta_{\beta}, \zeta_{\gamma}).$$

ii. *Monotonicity: If $\mathcal{P}_i \leq \mathcal{Q}_i$, that is, $\zeta_{\alpha_i} \leq \zeta_{\tilde{\alpha}_i}$, $\zeta_{\beta_i} \geq \zeta_{\tilde{\beta}_i}$, and $\zeta_{\gamma_i} \geq \zeta_{\tilde{\gamma}_i}$, then we have*

$$LPNEWG(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n) \leq LPNEWG(\mathcal{Q}_1, \mathcal{Q}_2, \mathcal{Q}_3, \dots, \mathcal{Q}_n).$$

iii. *Boundedness: Suppose $\mathcal{P}^- = \min(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n)$, $\mathcal{P}^+ = \max(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n)$, then*

$$\mathcal{P}^- \leq LPNEWG(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n) \leq \mathcal{P}^+.$$

The proof is analogous to Theorem 3.

4.4 LPN Einstein order weighted geometry (LPNEOWG) operator

Definition: 11 Set a LPNNs $\mathcal{P}_i = (\zeta_{\alpha_i}, \zeta_{\beta_i}, \zeta_{\gamma_i})$ in ζ , for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$, then the LPNEOWG operator is defined as: $LPNEOWA(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n) = \mathcal{P}_{\rho(1)}^{\omega_1} \otimes_{\epsilon} \mathcal{P}_{\rho(2)}^{\omega_2} \otimes_{\epsilon} \dots \mathcal{P}_{\rho(n)}^{\omega_n}$, where $(\rho(1), \rho(2), \rho(3), \dots, \rho(n))$ is a permutation of $(i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n)$, such that $\mathcal{P}_{\rho(i-1)} \geq \mathcal{P}_{\rho(i)}$ for each i , with the weight vector $\omega = (\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3, \dots, \omega_n)^T$, $\sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i = 1$ and $\omega_i \in [0, 1]$.

Theorem: 8 Set a collection $\mathcal{P}_i = (\zeta_{\alpha_i}, \zeta_{\beta_i}, \zeta_{\gamma_i})$ in ζ , for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n$, then the fusion result by LPNEOWG operator is obtained as:

$$LPNEOWA(\mathcal{P}_1, \mathcal{P}_2, \mathcal{P}_3, \dots, \mathcal{P}_n) = \left(\zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{2 \prod_{i=1}^n (\alpha_{\rho(i)})^{\omega_i}}{\prod_{i=1}^n (\alpha_{\rho(i)}^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^n (2t^2 - \alpha_{\rho(i)}^2)^{\omega_i}}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{\prod_{i=1}^n (t^2 + \beta_{\rho(i)}^2)^{\omega_i} - \prod_{i=1}^n (t^2 - \beta_{\rho(i)}^2)^{\omega_i}}{\prod_{i=1}^n (t^2 + \beta_{\rho(i)}^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^n (t^2 - \beta_{\rho(i)}^2)^{\omega_i}}}}, \zeta \sqrt[t]{\frac{\prod_{i=1}^n (t^2 + \gamma_{\rho(i)}^2)^{\omega_i} - \prod_{i=1}^n (t^2 - \gamma_{\rho(i)}^2)^{\omega_i}}{\prod_{i=1}^n (t^2 + \gamma_{\rho(i)}^2)^{\omega_i} + \prod_{i=1}^n (t^2 - \gamma_{\rho(i)}^2)^{\omega_i}}} \right)$$

where $(\rho(1), \rho(2), \rho(3), \dots, \rho(n))$ is a permutation of $(i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n)$, such that $\mathcal{P}_{\rho(i-1)} \geq \mathcal{P}_{\rho(i)}$ for each i . Let the weight vector be $\omega = (\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3, \dots, \omega_n)^T$, where $\sum_{i=1}^n \omega_i = 1$ and $\omega_i \in [0, 1]$. It is evident that

if $\omega = (\frac{1}{n}, \frac{1}{n}, \frac{1}{n}, \dots, \frac{1}{n})$, the LPNEOWG operator simplifies to the LPNWA operator. Furthermore

The LPNEOWG operator satisfies the conditions established in Theorem 3.

5. A Multi-Criteria based developed Decision-Making (MCDM) Framework

In this section, we propose a Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) approach based on LPNF operators to address decision-making (DM) problems involving LPN information, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. MCDM Flowchart

6. MCDM in Sustainable agriculture

Sustainable agriculture refers to farming practices that focus on producing food, fiber, or other agricultural products in a way that is environmentally sound, economically viable, and socially responsible. The goal of sustainable agriculture is to meet the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.

6.1 Factors affecting Agricultural Sustainability

- **Economic Factors: ($S\mathcal{F}_1$)**
- ❖ **Government Policies:** Government policies are important in shaping agricultural performance through subsidies, import and export controls and financing. Farm revenues are stabilized by offsetting market uncertainty, ensuring prices and augmenting income through input subsidies. Trade policy determines access to overseas markets and land use, while environmental legislation directs farm management and sustainability practices. Apart from this, rural credit policies allow the farmers to borrow money, and investment in irrigation and roads makes the processes efficient and reduces the cost. Thus, effective policies are necessary in order to maintain a sustainable and durable agriculture sector, and avoid economic instability, productivity constraints.
- ❖ **Market Price:** Market prices are the primary concern for agriculture production and profitability. During high prices, farmers are convinced to grow more, thus expecting more profit. Conversely, low prices lead to less profit, compelling farmers to reduce production, quality, or drop some of these crops. Price volatility caused by weather, shifts in world demand and supply chain, renders it uncertain for farmers to predict income and plan for expenditure. Thus, it results in inefficiencies like overproduction at the peak of prices and under production at the decline of prices, further destabilizing the market. To counter these risks, the government intervenes through the imposition of price supports, subsidies, or price floors to attempt to stabilize the market and provide a less risky return. This allows farmers to more effectively plan and invest in the future.
- **Physical Factors: ($S\mathcal{F}_2$)**
 - ❖ **Soil:** Soil characteristics have a direct influence on plant growth and crop development. Plant productivity and health are influenced by soil fertility, texture, nutrient status, and pH levels. Nutrient-rich soil containing nutrients like nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium support crop growth. Soil texture affects water holding capacity and drainage. Clayey soil holds water, whereas sandy soil drains rapidly, resulting in root health consequences. Its pH influences nutrient availability owing to the fact that various plants have different optimal levels of pH. Organic matter and microorganisms in the soil also increase fertility by cycling nutrients and maintaining aggregates together. Agricultural productivity and soil health are ensured through

efficient soil management practices like crop rotation, fertilization, and anti-erosion measures, hence reducing erosion and nutrient loss.

❖ **Topography:** Topography has an influence on water drainage, soil erosion, crop choice, and farming efficiency. Slopes with a higher degree produce quicker runoff of water, which raises the possibility of soil erosion and lowers fertility, whereas flat land promotes more water retention as well as ease of tilling. Altitude controls temperature and season as higher altitudes have lower temperatures that restrict crop choice, while lower altitudes have higher temperatures and can be cultivated with longer-term crops. This also affects soil fertility. Valleys have more fertile lands, while hilly terrains have less fertile and shallow soil. It also complicates mechanization, which raises equipment and labor expenses. In general, it regulates land suitability for agriculture.

● **Climatic Factors: (SF_3)**

❖ **Precipitation:**

Rainfall is crucial in farm sustainability as it affects water availability and plant growth. Frequent and periodic precipitation ensures that plants receive adequate water while growing, thus reducing irrigation requirements and improving soil fertility. Heavy rainfall might cause water logging, which smothers root growth and kills nutrient uptake, causing soil erosion and plant disease. Conversely, light rainfall, particularly during cropping periods, may lead to drought, by depleting soil water and reducing farm production. Drought also increases the reliance on irrigation, and other water resources. To overcome these, farmers implement practices like rainwater collection, soil moisture conservation, and the planting of drought-tolerant crops to provide more reliable agricultural yields under precipitation variability.

❖ **Global Warming:**

Global Warming interferes with climatic patterns, by altering the growing seasons, and enhancing the frequency of extreme weather events. Temperature increase can decrease crop yields, especially where the heat is more intense, by shifting the planting and harvesting season. Severe events such as droughts, floods, and heatwaves enhance the health risks to crops, resulting in reduced productivity and increased susceptibility to pests and diseases. These changes complicate irrigation and water management, added to it increasing evaporation rates create even more pressure on soil moisture. This can be reduced by using drought-resistant plants, better water management practices, and other methods to deal with the effects of global warming on agriculture.

● **Human Factors: (SF_4)**

❖ **Labour:**

Labor requirements impact the cost of production, efficiency, and scalability. Excessive requirements increase costs and introduce inefficiencies, especially if labor is limited or expensive it delays planting and harvest or reduces yield. Mechanization or automation reduces labor needs, increases production, and saves labour costs but, on the other hand, displaces work, particularly rural, and it is also expensive. Equilibrating labor needs and technology procurement is key to achieving the economic viability and job generation of agriculture.

❖ Technology:

Technology increases productivity, efficiency, and sustainability. Precision farming devices such as the use of GPS, sensors, and drones enable the farmers to optimize water, fertilizer, and pesticide application for greater production and reduced wastage. Mechanization in terms of planting and harvesting equipment reduces labor costs. Genetically modified crop organisms (GMOs) provide protection from insects and diseases, enhancing crop lifespan. Automatic irrigation systems reduce water loss. Thus, it has revolutionized agriculture by increasing efficiency, yield, and sustainability along with drawbacks like high cost, loss of jobs, and environmental degradation.

● **Infrastructure:**

❖ Electricity:

Electricity is crucial for major agricultural practices. Electric pumps facilitate effective irrigation while cold stores and grain drying houses reduce post-harvest loss by using significant amounts of energy. Precision farming equipment like drones and AI-based monitoring relies on electricity to monitor in real time. However, increased electricity costs and fluctuation in power supply area might limit the profitability and viability of the farms. Achieving cost, energy efficiency, and sustainability is a core element towards sustainable agriculture.

❖ Transport & Storage:

Transport and storage are crucial to food security, profitability, and efficiency. There is assured timely delivery, reduced spoilage, and enhanced market access through sufficient transport, while poor infrastructure and high fuel prices translate into losses and delays. The quality of products is maintained by proper storage like cold storage and silos by avoiding pest infestation and spoilage, while low facilities are responsible for wastage of food resulting in price volatility. Development of transportation and storage facilities aids in market stabilization and loss reduction, thus aiding agricultural development.

● **Institutional Factors: (SF_5)**

❖ Land Tenure & Tenancy:

Land tenure and tenorial systems also play an important role in farm investment, efficiency, and land use. Stable holding triggers farmers' investment in long-term investments like irrigation, soil conservation, and sustainable productivity, thus boosting output and efficiency. Unstable tenure or property rights, discourages investment and may lead to land degradation. Tenancy contracts such as short leases or high rents tend to limit farmers from enhancing, thus reducing productivity and security. Land restrictive policies and unequal land access also displace small-scale farmers, and agricultural development becomes difficult. A good land tenure system that offers security, equal access, and fair tenancy contracts encourages productive and sustainable agriculture.

❖ Land Reforms:

Land reform reshapes farm productivity by redistributing land, enhancing access for small farmers, and promoting equitable ownership. It allows farmers to access credit, investments in irrigation and other facilities. It brings in new technologies, thereby increasing efficiency and production. It also relieves rural poverty through the availability of self-sufficiency for landless farmers. But

improper reforms will most likely be responsible for producing excess land fragmentation, and ownership disputes. Successful land reform can be achieved alone with well-designed policy interventions, through economic assistance, technical education, and the establishment of infrastructure in an attempt to realize long-term farm development and expansion.

Fig. 2. Fishbone diagram of factors affecting Agricultural Sustainability

Fig. 3. Major contributing factors affecting Agricultural Sustainability

We formulate the above problem as an MCDM problem to identify the most influential factor among Economic, Physical, Infrastructure, Climatic, Institutional and Human factors using the Linguistic Pythagorean Neutrosophic Einstein Weighted Average and Linguistic Pythagorean Neutrosophic Einstein Weighted Geometric operators. Both operators exhibit linear time complexity $O(n)$, require only basic arithmetic operations without iterations or matrix computations, and are thus computationally efficient and scalable for large-scale decision-making involving numerous criteria or alternatives.

SDG2 focuses on ending hunger, achieving food security and improved nutrition and promoting sustainable agriculture. In the Indian agriculture sector, companies like Godrej Agrovvet, AgNext Technologies, and Coromandel International are known for their sustainability initiatives and focus on sustainable farming practices.

In this work, we consider four of these companies $\mathfrak{C} = (\mathfrak{C}_1, \mathfrak{C}_2, \mathfrak{C}_3, \mathfrak{C}_4)$ in India depends on their product selling strategies for achieving sustainability in agriculture. based on these factors how the companies can maintain their sustainability in the agriculture field. There are decision makers/experts $\mathfrak{D} = (\mathfrak{D}_1, \mathfrak{D}_2, \mathfrak{D}_3)$ are invited to evaluate according to six factors based on the company's performance with weight vector is $w = (0.37, 0.33, 0.3)$. The evaluations based on the experts make evaluations on the four alternative factors $\mathfrak{SF} = (\mathfrak{SF}_1, \mathfrak{SF}_2, \mathfrak{SF}_3, \mathfrak{SF}_4)$ with the weight vector $\mathcal{W}_f = (0.26, 0.24, 0.21, 0.29)$. Now, the experts use LPNNs to make the evaluation values with a linguistic set $\zeta = \{\zeta_0 = \textit{extremely poor}, \zeta_1 = \textit{very poor}, \zeta_2 = \textit{poor}, \zeta_3 = \textit{slightly poor}, \zeta_4 = \textit{medium}, \zeta_5 = \textit{slightly good}, \zeta_6 = \textit{good}, \zeta_7 = \textit{very good}, \zeta_8 = \textit{extremely good}\}$. The decision evaluation matrix are given below (tables 1– 4).

Table 1: The first decision maker \mathfrak{D}_1 gives the following values in the matrix form

	\mathfrak{SF}_1	\mathfrak{SF}_2	\mathfrak{SF}_3	\mathfrak{SF}_4
\mathfrak{C}_1	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_1, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_7, \zeta_1, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_8, \zeta_1, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_5, \zeta_2, \zeta_3)$
\mathfrak{C}_2	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_2, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_7, \zeta_5)$	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_6, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_5, \zeta_3, \zeta_3)$
\mathfrak{C}_3	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_3, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_4, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_1, \zeta_6)$	$(\zeta_5, \zeta_3, \zeta_3)$
\mathfrak{C}_4	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_2, \zeta_2)$	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_1, \zeta_5)$	$(\zeta_8, \zeta_1, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_3, \zeta_3)$

Table 2: The second decision maker \mathfrak{D}_2 gives the following values in the matrix form

	\mathfrak{SF}_1	\mathfrak{SF}_2	\mathfrak{SF}_3	\mathfrak{SF}_4
\mathfrak{C}_1	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_2, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_7, \zeta_4, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_1, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_3, \zeta_3)$
\mathfrak{C}_2	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_2, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_7, \zeta_1, \zeta_4)$	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_1, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_7, \zeta_2, \zeta_3)$
\mathfrak{C}_3	$(\zeta_5, \zeta_3, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_5, \zeta_2, \zeta_4)$	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_1, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_8, \zeta_3, \zeta_3)$
\mathfrak{C}_4	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_4, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_5, \zeta_4, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_1, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_5, \zeta_2, \zeta_3)$

Table 3: The third decision maker \mathfrak{D}_3 gives the following values in the matrix form

	\mathfrak{SF}_1	\mathfrak{SF}_2	\mathfrak{SF}_3	\mathfrak{SF}_4
\mathfrak{C}_1	$(\zeta_7, \zeta_1, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_2, \zeta_5)$	$(\zeta_3, \zeta_3, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_8, \zeta_1, \zeta_3)$
\mathfrak{C}_2	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_4, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_2, \zeta_5)$	$(\zeta_5, \zeta_5, \zeta_5)$	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_2, \zeta_2)$
\mathfrak{C}_3	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_1, \zeta_4)$	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_5, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_5, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_2, \zeta_3)$
\mathfrak{C}_4	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_1, \zeta_5)$	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_5, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_4, \zeta_4, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_6, \zeta_3, \zeta_3)$

Based on the **LPNEWA and LPNEWG operators**, we solve the above decision-making problem in the following manner and the obtained values are in Table 5 and Table 6.

Table 5. The overall decision matrix

	SF_1	SF_2	SF_3	SF_4
\mathfrak{C}_1	$(\zeta_{6.0397}, \zeta_{1.1230}, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_{6.6098}, \zeta_{1.4128}, \zeta_{3.5219})$	$(\zeta_8, \zeta_{1.1862}, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_8, \zeta_{1.2946}, \zeta_3)$
\mathfrak{C}_2	$(\zeta_{5.7547}, \zeta_{1.17956}, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_{6.2061}, \zeta_{2.6956}, \zeta_{4.6548})$	$(\zeta_{5.5650}, \zeta_{2.5979}, \zeta_{3.5219})$	$(\zeta_{5.3915}, \zeta_{1.6758}, \zeta_{2.6612})$
\mathfrak{C}_3	$(\zeta_{5.4334}, \zeta_{1.8142}, \zeta_{3.2762})$	$(\zeta_{5.4334}, \zeta_{2.4168}, \zeta_{3.3049})$	$(\zeta_{5.7547}, \zeta_{1.3046}, \zeta_{3.9515})$	$(\zeta_{5.3915}, \zeta_{1.6758}, \zeta_3)$
\mathfrak{C}_4	$(\zeta_{5.7547}, \zeta_{1.6443}, \zeta_{3.0485})$	$(\zeta_{5.4334}, \zeta_{1.6460}, \zeta_{3.6536})$	$(\zeta_8, \zeta_{1.2478}, \zeta_3)$	$(\zeta_{5.4334}, \zeta_{1.9888}, \zeta_3)$

Step 2: The total collective LPNN \mathfrak{C}_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, m$) can be obtained by the LPNEWA operator:

$$\mathfrak{C}_1 = (\zeta_8, \zeta_{2.3655}, \zeta_{3.1190}); \mathfrak{C}_2 = (\zeta_{5.0618}, \zeta_{3.1022}, \zeta_{3.3464});$$

$$\mathfrak{C}_3 = (\zeta_{4.7291}, \zeta_{3.2301}, \zeta_{3.3319}); \mathfrak{C}_4 = (\zeta_{7.6441}, \zeta_{3.0416}, \zeta_{3.1604})$$

Step 3: By using definition 5, we calculate the expected values of $\mathfrak{X}(\mathfrak{C}_i)$ for \mathfrak{C}_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$)

$$\mathfrak{X}(\mathfrak{C}_1) = 6.1285; \mathfrak{X}(\mathfrak{C}_2) = 4.7889; \mathfrak{X}(\mathfrak{C}_3) = 4.6486; \mathfrak{X}(\mathfrak{C}_4) = 5.8649.$$

Based on the expected values, four alternatives can be ranked $\mathfrak{C}_1 > \mathfrak{C}_4 > \mathfrak{C}_2 > \mathfrak{C}_3$. Thus, company \mathfrak{C}_3 is the optimal choice.

Now, we find the optimal choice using the LPNEWG operator.

Table 6. The overall decision matrix

	SF_1	SF_2	SF_3	SF_4
\mathfrak{C}_1	$(\zeta_{3.5005}, \zeta_{1.3752}, \zeta_{2.848})$	$(\zeta_{3.7147}, \zeta_{2.558}, \zeta_{3.391})$	$(\zeta_{3.589}, \zeta_{1.585}, \zeta_{3.391})$	$(\zeta_{3.392}, \zeta_{1.418}, \zeta_{2.848})$
\mathfrak{C}_2	$(\zeta_{3.4122}, \zeta_{2.4606}, \zeta_{2.848})$	$(\zeta_{3.5091}, \zeta_{4.968}, \zeta_{4.447})$	$(\zeta_{3.327}, \zeta_{4.471}, \zeta_{3.391})$	$(\zeta_{3.197}, \zeta_{2.116}, \zeta_{2.667})$
\mathfrak{C}_3	$(\zeta_{3.3187}, \zeta_{2.5533}, \zeta_{3.089})$	$(\zeta_{3.3187}, \zeta_{3.534}, \zeta_{4.447})$	$(\zeta_{3.412}, \zeta_{2.442}, \zeta_{4.388})$	$(\zeta_{3.197}, \zeta_{2.116}, \zeta_{2.848})$
\mathfrak{C}_4	$(\zeta_{3.4122}, \zeta_{2.6547}, \zeta_{3.111})$	$(\zeta_{3.3187}, \zeta_{3.307}, \zeta_{3.785})$	$(\zeta_{3.685}, \zeta_{1.991}, \zeta_{2.848})$	$(\zeta_{3.319}, \zeta_{2.542}, \zeta_{2.848})$

Step 2: The total collective LPNN \mathfrak{C}_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, m$) can be obtained by the LPNEWA operator:

$$\mathfrak{C}_1 = (\zeta_{4.8605}, \zeta_{1.5982}, \zeta_{2.593}); \mathfrak{C}_2 = (\zeta_{4.6882}, \zeta_{3.4566}, \zeta_{3.093});$$

$$\mathfrak{C}_3 = (\zeta_{4.6193}, \zeta_{2.4321}, \zeta_{3.054}); \mathfrak{C}_4 = (\zeta_{4.7284}, \zeta_{2.2984}, \zeta_{2.803})$$

Step 3: By using definition 5, we calculate the expected values of $\mathfrak{X}(\mathfrak{C}_i)$ for \mathfrak{C}_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4$)

$$\mathfrak{X}(\mathfrak{C}_1) = 5.1103; \mathfrak{X}(\mathfrak{C}_2) = 4.6356; \mathfrak{X}(\mathfrak{C}_3) = 4.8338; \mathfrak{X}(\mathfrak{C}_4) = 4.9402.$$

Based on the expected values, four alternatives can be ranked $\mathfrak{C}_1 > \mathfrak{C}_4 > \mathfrak{C}_3 > \mathfrak{C}_2$. Thus, company \mathfrak{C}_2 is the optimal choice.

6.2 Comparative Analysis

We compare the proposed LPNEWA and LPNEWG methods with other LIFEWA and LPFEWA approaches. The results of this comparison are presented in Figure 4.

From Figure 4, it is evident that alternatives \mathfrak{C}_3 and \mathfrak{C}_2 emerge as the most optimal choices when evaluated using the LPNEWA and LPNEWG methods. The ranking orders produced by these two methods are: $\mathfrak{C}_1 > \mathfrak{C}_4 > \mathfrak{C}_2 > \mathfrak{C}_3$ for LPNEWA, and $\mathfrak{C}_1 > \mathfrak{C}_4 > \mathfrak{C}_3 > \mathfrak{C}_2$. for LPNEWG. To validate the effectiveness of the proposed method, a comparison is made with existing approaches, including the linguistic intuitionistic fuzzy weighted average (LIFWA) operator introduced by Chen et al. [25], the LPF weighted average (LPFEWA) operator developed by Garg [26], Sine Single-Valued

Neutrosophic Einstein Weighted Averaging (S-SvNVEWA) and Sine Single-Valued Neutrosophic Einstein Weighted Geometric (S-SvNVEWG) aggregation operators developed by Zhang et al. [27]. Unlike these earlier methods [25–27], the proposed LPNN-based approach can effectively represent and handle purely linguistic evaluation values—something that traditional MCDM methods cannot achieve. By integrating LPNS with Einstein operations, the proposed method clearly demonstrates its flexibility and effectiveness.

Fig. 4. Comparative analysis of different MCDM methods

7. Conclusion

This paper proposed a novel approach to solving MCDM problems. Initially, the Einstein operation was applied to Linguistic Pythagorean Neutrosophic Numbers (LPNNs), and new operational rules were established based on this operator. Subsequently, several aggregation operators were integrated with the LPNNs to define the Linguistic Pythagorean Neutrosophic Einstein Weighted Average (LPNEWA) operator and the Linguistic Pythagorean Neutrosophic Einstein Weighted Geometric (LPNEWG) operator, in accordance with the newly developed rules. Using the LPNEWA and LPNEWG operators, two methods were introduced to effectively address MCDM problems. To demonstrate the practicality and benefits of the proposed methods, they were applied to a real-world example.

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References:

1. Smarandache, F. Neutrosophy: Neutrosophic Probability, Set, and Logic, ProQuest Information & Learning; Infolearnquest: Ann Arbor, MI, USA, 1998; p. 105.
2. F. Al-Sharqi, A.G. Ahmad, A. Al-Quran, Fuzzy parameterized-interval complex neutrosophic soft sets and their applications under uncertainty, *Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems*, vol. 44, pp.1453–1477, 2023.
3. Mamites, I., Almerino, P., Sitoy, R., Atibing, N. M., Almerino, J. G., Cebe, D., Ybañez, R., Tandag, J., Villaganas, M. A., Lumayag, C., Plando, D., Añero, M., Acebes, H. M., Maturan, F., Evangelista, S. S., Aro, J. L., Himang, C., & Ocampo, L. (2022). Factors Influencing Teaching Quality in Universities: Analyzing Causal Relationships Based on Neutrosophic DEMATEL. *Education Research International*, 2022. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/9475254>
4. S. Narasimman, M. Shanmugapriya, R. Sundareswaran, Laxmi Rathour, Lakshmi Narayan Mishra, Vinita Dewangan and Vishnu Narayan Mishra, "Identification of influential factors affecting student performance in semester examinations in the educational institution using score topological indices in Single Valued Neutrosophic Graphs" *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, Vol. 75, pp. 224-240, 2024.
5. B. Amudha, M. Shanmugapriya, R. Sundareswaran and Said Broumi, "Numerical and Semi Analytical Scheme for developing a solution to Falkner Skan equation in Neutrosophic environments", *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, Vol. 79, pp. 188-215, 2025.
6. Zadeh, L.A. The concept of a linguistic variable and its application to approximate reasoning Part I. *Inf. Sci.* **1975**, *8*, 199-249.
7. Fang, Z.; Ye J. Multiple attribute group decision-making method based on linguistic neutrosophic numbers. *Symmetry* **2017**, *9*, 111.
8. Fan, C.; Ye, J.; Hu, K.; Fan, E. Bonferroni Mean Operators of Linguistic Neutrosophic Numbers and Their Multiple Attribute Group Decision-Making Methods. *Information* **2017**, *8*, 107. doi:10.3390/info8030107.
9. Li, Y.Y.; Zhang, H.Y.; Wang, J.Q. Linguistic Neutrosophic Sets and Their Application in Multicriteria Decision-Making Problems. *Int. J. Uncertain. Quantif.* **2017**, *7*, 135–154.
10. Shi, L.; Ye, J. Cosine Measures of Linguistic Neutrosophic Numbers and Their Application in Multiple Attribute Group Decision-Making. *Information* **2017**, *8*, 10.
11. Cui, W.H.; Ye, J. Multiple-attribute decision-making method using similarity measures of hesitant linguistic neutrosophic numbers regarding least common multiple cardinality. *Symmetry* **2018**, *10*, 330.
12. Lu, X.P.; Ye, J. Similarity Measures of Linguistic Cubic Hesitant Variables for Multiple Attribute Group Decision-Making. *Information* **2019**, *10*, 168.
13. Zhao, H.; Xu, Z.S.; Ni, M.F.; Liu, S.S. Generalized Aggregation Operators for Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets. *Int. J. Intell. Syst.* **2010**, *25*, 1–30.
14. Wang, W.Z.; Liu, X.W. Intuitionistic fuzzy geometric aggregation operators based on Einstein operations. *Int. J. Intell. Syst.* **2011**, *26*, 1049–1075.

15. Zhao, X.F.; Wei, G.W. Some intuitionistic fuzzy Einstein hybrid aggregation operators and their application to multiple attribute decision making. *Knowl. Based Syst.* 2013, *37*,472–479.
16. Guo, S.; Jin, F.F.; Chen, Y.H. Application of hesitate fuzzy Einstein geometry operator. *Comput. Eng. Appl.* 2013.
17. Li, B., Wang, J., Yang, L., & Li, X. (2018). A novel generalized simplified neutrosophic number Einstein aggregation operator. *Infinite Study*.
18. Farid, H.M.A., Garg, H., Riaz, M. and Santos-García, G. (2023), "Multi-criteria group decision-making algorithm based on single-valued neutrosophic Einstein prioritized aggregation operators and its applications", *Management Decision*, Vol. 61 No. 2, pp. 382-420.
19. Khan, M., Gulistan, M., Yaqoob, N., Khan, M., & Smarandache, F. (2019). Neutrosophic Cubic Einstein Geometric Aggregation Operators with Application to Multi-Criteria Decision-Making Method. *Symmetry*, *11*(2), 247.
20. Ye, J., Türkarlan, E., Ünver, M. *et al.* Algebraic and Einstein weighted operators of neutrosophic enthalpy values for multi-criteria decision making in neutrosophic multi-valued set settings. *Granul. Comput.* *7*, 479–487 (2022).
21. Xu, Minna; Rui Yong; and Yohannes Belayne. "Decision Making Methods with Linguistic Neutrosophic Information: A Review." *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems* *38*, 1 (2020).
22. Fan, C., Feng, S., & Hu, K. (2019). Linguistic Neutrosophic Numbers Einstein Operator and Its Application in Decision Making. *Mathematics*, *7*(5), 389.
23. Jamil, M.; Afzal, F.;Akgül, A.; Abdullah, S.; Maqbool, A.;Razzaque, A.; Riaz, M.B.;Awrejcewicz, J. Einstein Aggregation Operators under Bipolar Neutrosophic Environment with Applications in Multi-Criteria Decision-Making. *Appl. Sci.* **2022**, *12*, 10045.
24. Garg, H. Linguistic Pythagorean fuzzy sets and its applications in multiattribute decision-making process. *Int. J. Intell. Syst.* 2018, *33*, 1234–1263.
25. Chen, Z.; Liu, P.; Pei, Z. An approach to multiple attribute group decision making based on linguistic intuitionistic fuzzy numbers. *Int. J. Comput. Intell. Syst.* 2015, *8*, 747–760.
26. Garg, H. Linguistic Pythagorean fuzzy sets and its applications in multiattribute decision-making process. *Int. J. Intell. Syst.* 2018, *33*, 1234–1263.
27. Zhang, T., Lu, X., Chen, K., Liu, C., & Ye, J. Evaluation of Practice-Based Curriculum Objectives Achievement Degree Using Einstein Aggregation Operators of Single-Valued Neutrosophic Credibility Numbers. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 2025, *86*, 159-170.

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